

SOME REFLECTIONS ON THE TEACHING OF ISHAKHKHAN TORAH

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Annotation: This article shares some information about Is'haq Khan Ibrat and his life and genealogy, as well as some information about his contribution to science, the schools he opened, and the good deeds he did.

Keywords: scientist, nation, work, country, religion, reform, poet, reform, culture, tourist, Uzbek literature.

The land of Namangan has an ancient and sacred, distant history, many great figures have stepped on it, and their navel blood has dripped on it. One of the famous people who grew up in Namangan is Ishaqkhan Ibrat, a great enlightener and scientist.

As a poet and scientist, publisher and pedagogue, religious figure and reformer, Ishaq Khan Ibrat devoted his life to the benefit of the Motherland and the nation. Therefore, its rich cultural heritage is widely studied not only in our country, but also near and far abroad. This opinion is supported by the publication of the scientist's work "Mezon uz-zaman" in cooperation with Japanese scientists, and the publication of his poems with a significant foreword in Turkey.[1]

Ibrat, son of Ishaq Khan Junaydullakhkhoja (1862-1937), is one of the figures in the history of Turkestan Jadidism, along with M. Bekhbudi, M. Abdurashidkhanov, due to his role in Fergana, the scope of his activities, his works, his dedication to the homeland, the people, and the nation.

He is a contemporary figure, historian, scholar, famous poet, linguist, article writer, publisher, translator, calligrapher, world traveler and teacher.

Information from his scientific, pedagogical and artistic works such as "Lug'ati Sittati Alsina", "Jome ul-Khutut", "History of Fergana", "Mezon uz-zaman", "San'ati Ibrat, kalami Mirrajab Bandi", memories of his contemporaries who knew Ibrat closely, and articles about Ishaq Khan Ibrat published in the press of that time, play an important role in the complete coverage of the poet's biography. Ishaq Khan Ibrat was born in 1862 in the village of Torakorgan near Namangan.[2]

The work "History of Fergana" written by Ishaq Khan Ibrat in 1916, which has reached us, is a historical source that provides excellent information about the early periods of his life and activity. In the "Introduction" part of the work, he wrote that he was born in Torakorgan, one of the settlements of the Kokhan Khanate in the Ferghana Valley, which belongs to the climate of Turkestan.[3]

This information is given in his poem "Historical Bath" published in "Gazette of Turkestan Province" in 1905, and in his poetry collection "Ilmi Ibrat" written in 1909.[4]

Ishaq Khan Ibrat's parents were among the educated people of Junaydullakhkhoja and Khuribibi period. Ishaq Khan first studied in a village school based on the hijra method, but he learned literacy under the hands of his mother. Huribibi was a school teacher and did not limit herself to rote memorization at her school, she also taught girls how to write and write. He was very literate and was aware of husnikhat. That is why Ishaq Khan respects his mother in many places as his mentor.

According to the sources, Ibrat is a descendant of Ahmed Yassavi in terms of genealogy. This is evidenced by the “Genealogy” preserved in the hands of his descendants. According to it, it is written: “Junaidullakh Khoja is an undoubted successor, a descendant of the pious Said Alim Sultan Khoja Ahmed Yassavi”. [5]

Look at this, for a quarter of a century, the Namangan historian Burkhoniddin aka Nizomov also determined the date of birth of Ibrat. At the same time, he talked with the grateful Tursunboy Obidov about Ibrat: “One day my grandmother Junaydullakh khan went out to find my house”, said Tursunboy Obidov at that time. - During Nowruz holiday, grandmother’s baked chalpak (doughy dish made by thinly spreading zuvala and frying in oil) was liked and praised by the sons of Tora. Then Khurbibi said, “As far as I know, Ishaq khan loves hats, and he was born on Nowruz day”. My grandmother heard that saying, and every Navroz, they did not forget to cook chappals and kiss teacher Ibrat. “Today is my daughter’s birthday, I heard it from my grandmother Khurbibi with my own ears,” they said. It can be seen that Maulana Ibrat was born on March 21. [6]

The years of Ishaq Khan Ibrat’s education at the Kokan madrasa (1878-1886) correspond to the period of fundamental qualitative changes in Uzbek literature, cultural life, and education. There is no doubt that he enjoyed this literary and cultural life. [7] According to Furkat’s article “Sarguzashtnoma” from the pages of “Gazette of Turkestan Region”, one of the local sources, when Ibrat studied at the madrasa, that is, in the 80s of the XIX century, social life and culture in Kokan was somewhat advanced compared to other cities of Central Asia.

In recent researches about the first Jadid school [8] established at the end of the 19th century in Turkestan, including the work of A. Khudoykulov, the merchant Khusainov School opened in 1893 in Samarkand [9] is shown, while G. Solijonova cited the Salakhiddin teacher’s school opened in Andijan in 1898 as the first Jadid school. However, today’s information indicates that the first Jadid school in Turkestan was opened in 1886 by Ibrat, the son of Ishaq khan Junaydullakh-Khoja. The first information about the school opened by Ishaq khan Ibrat is given in his poem “Kalam”. [10]

According to the information on the pages of the diary of the BARS-51 group written by Y. Gaffarov, the creation of a new school system was a progressive idea in Turkestan, and the struggle between the ancient and the modern played an important role in Ibrat’s work.

According to the sources collected based on interviews with Ibrat’s contemporaries, relatives, and descendants, and according to the information given by his son R. Ishakov, he opened the Jadid school after graduating from the Siddiq Tunqator madrasa before he went abroad. [11]

It is clear from this that if we take into account that Ibrat graduated from the Siddiq Tunqator madrasa in 1886 and went on a trip abroad in 1887, he opened a new school during this period.

In the years 1878-1886, when he was a student at the madrasa, Ibrat was regularly familiar with the newspaper “Tarjiman” published in Bogchasaroy. Through these publications, he learned about the advantages of the new method school, educational methods, the structure of classrooms and textbooks, and after graduating from the madrasa, he returned to Torakorgan and opened a modern school in 1886. [12]

Is’haq Khan Ibrat did not limit himself to the sciences taught by the madrasa. During his

studies, he independently diligently read the works of great Eastern scientists, studied Arabic, Persian and Russian languages in depth. He first got acquainted with the first newspapers of Turkestan published in Russian and Uzbek languages, "Gazette of Turkestan Region", "Turkestarskie Vedomosti" and Ismailbek Gasprali's "Tarjiman" newspaper, which was newly published in Turkestan, when he was studying at the Koqan madrasa. According to information, the "Is'hakiya" library, founded by Ishaq Khan, even had volumes of the "Tarjiman" newspaper from 1884. [13]

In 1886, Ishaq Khan Tora Ibrat graduated from the Koqan madrasa and returned to his village Torakurgan. He began his career as an advanced educator by spreading enlightenment: that year he opened a school in his village. His school was somewhat different from schools based on the "usuli qadim" schools based on the Hija method. While studying in Kogan, Ibrat noticed the superiority of the teaching methods of the Russian schools opened in the country over the rote and rote memorization prevailing in the local schools. Is'haq Khan applied the sound (savtiya) method, which was more advanced than his school, and defended the "method savtiya" from the supporters of the old method. However, he could not work in this school for a long time. Some ignorant fanatics declared his school as a "school of infidels" and tried to turn away the children of the people from this school. They even managed to close it with the help of the officials of the General Governorate. [14]

According to Ibrat in his works "Lug'ati sittati alsina", "Jome ul-khutut" and "Tarihi Fergana", in 1887, that is, at the age of 25, he took his mother to Mecca for the pilgrimage. However, his mother was not lucky enough to return to her homeland. Her mother, Huribibi, died of pneumonia in Jeddah.

Ishaq Khan's main purpose for traveling to Eastern countries was, firstly, to satisfy his mother's request to take him on Hajj, and secondly, he wanted to get to know the life and culture of foreign peoples, to see these countries with his own eyes: "...I died with the desire to spend my life's money in the market of lust, and when I was twenty-five years old, I traveled to the venerable Dushub because of the weather..." [15] - he writes.

Ishaq Khan Ibrat buried his mother in Jeddah and continued his journey through Eastern countries. At the same time, he visited the central cities of Europe, such as Istanbul, Sofia, Athens, and Rome. He lived for a long time in big cities like Kabul in Afghanistan and Jeddah in Arabia. From Mecca he came to India through the Red Sea and the Indian Ocean. In 1892-1896, he lived in Bombay and Calcutta, one of the largest port cities in India.[16]

Here he perfectly learned the Arba language, that is, four languages: Arabic, Persian, Indo-Urdu and English. Abroad, he had the opportunity to compare the life, culture and art of Eastern and Western nations.

As mentioned above, Ibrat opened a school in 1886 that was somewhat more advanced than the old schools. In 1907, he established a new school "Usuli Savtiya". He taught 25 village children in this school. The school is located in its own house - in a bright, windowed room, equipped with new educational equipment - desks, tables and chairs, new books, textbooks, notebooks, blackboards, kurrai arz (globes). He conducted his teaching work based on the program he created. In his school, Ishaq Khan Ibrat used Saidrasul Saidazizov's "Ustodi avval", "Muallim us-saniy" by Ali Askar Kalinin, "Adibi avval" by Munavvargari, as well as his own works "Lug'ati sittati alsina", "San`ati Ibrat, pen Mirrajab Bandiy" as textbooks and manuals.[17]

The last years of Ishaq Khan Ibrat's life were quite dangerous. First, old age, and secondly, since 1935, he was exempted from all positions, and old age pension was not assigned. On top of that, the administration of the local government looked at him with distrust, and the clouds of terrible repression were gathering over Ibrat.

Repression among the virtuous people of our country, Ishaq Khan Ibrat was drawn to his side like a dragon. The old poet who denounced the 75-year-old and a “black car” full of books were taken to Andijan prison. Ishaq Khan Ibrat spent several months in Stalin’s prison and said goodbye to life. The 75-year-old enlightened poet, who devoted his whole life for the enlightenment and independence of his people, could not bear the physical and mental pains of prison.

I conclude that such enlightened people are not born all the time, unfortunately, it is difficult to count the weight of such people among us, historical experience has shown that if a policy against science is carried out, especially during the former colonial period, there will be an increase in science, but if a wide opportunity is created for the development of science, not everyone will take advantage of this opportunity. Scholars, enlighteners and thinkers like Ibrat tried to go to Chin-mochin in the path of science in spite of difficult circumstances, but the authoritarian regime did everything against the intellectuals and turned almost all of them into victims of repression.

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